

Recurrent Furunculosis due to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Infection in A Four-month-old Infant: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Furunculosis is an acute infection that occurs in the hair follicles, causing abscess formation with pus and necrotic tissue accumulation within. Recurrent furunculosis is defined as having three or more recurring infection within 12 months. Several factors that may contribute are a family history of recurrent furunculosis, anaemia, prior antibiotic therapy, diabetes mellitus, history of the previous hospitalization, multiple lesion, poor hygiene, and other related diseases. Current therapy for recurrent furunculosis are both difficult and often show poor result. Antibiotics are recommended if there are signs of severe infection, such as multiple affected skin areas or the infection progressed quickly.

We reported a case of a male infant aged four months old and was diagnosed with recurrent furunculosis due to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infection. A combination of systemic cefadroxil and metronidazole treatment showed a good response.

KEYWORDS antibiotics, furunculosis, recurrent

Introduction

Furunculosis is an acute infection of the hair follicle that caused an abscess formation, filled with pus and necrotic tissue. The most common pathogen is *Staphylococcus aureus*, however other bacteria may act like the less common pathogen. It often occurs in several skin areas, such as the face, neck, axilla, buttocks, and groin. Furunculosis is more often found in male than female. [1,2,3,4] Recurrent furunculosis is defined as having three or more recurring infection within 12 months. Several factors that may contribute are a family history of recurrent furunculosis, anaemia, prior antibiotic therapy, diabetes mellitus, history of the previous hospitalization, multiple lesion, poor hygiene, and other related diseases. [5]

Several clinical manifestations of furunculosis are deep erythema, tenderness, and papules that evolve to nodules. The surrounding area may further develop into cellulitis. [4]

Laboratory examination such as pus culture is often required to determine the sensitivity of pathogens towards specific antibiotics and to identify potential Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (MRSA) infection. Gram staining may help to differentiate other pathogens besides *Staphylococcus aureus* that caused furunculosis. [4]

The differential diagnosis of furunculosis is cystic acne, kerion, hidradenitis suppurativa, epidermal cyst rupture, furuncular myiasis, and osteomyelitis. [1]

There are several treatment options to manage furuncle. Warm compress may help to reduce the symptoms in simple furuncle. The more significant and cystic lesion may need a small incision to drain the pus and necrotic tissues. Systemic antibiotics are needed in some cases in which the furuncle is located at the nasal area or external auditory canal, large and recurrent, cellulitis is present, and did not respond to local treatments. [6]

We reported a case of a four months old male infant, diagnosed with recurrent furunculosis due to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and show good response towards a combination of two systemic antibiotics, cefadroxil and metronidazole.

Case Report

A four-month-old male infant was brought to Dermatology and Venereology Clinics with the chief complaint of multiple vesicles on the head and neck since one month ago. Initially, there were

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Figure 1: First day visit

a-d: multiple erythema nodules, pustules, and crusts on the scalp, neck, anterior and posterior trunk

three vesicles which were treated with topical gentamicin cream from a primary health care centre. The vesicles healed in one week. However, the vesicles started to reappear afterwards. He was then treated with oral antibiotics given by the primary health care centre. The vesicles started to heal, but not long after, the vesicles started to reappear. One week before a hospital visit, the vesicles were treated with turmeric powder by his parents. History of fever and diarrhoea were denied. The family history of similar condition was denied. No drug or food allergy reported by his parents.

Upon physical examination, the general condition was good, and the body weight was 6,4 kg. Upon inspection of the scalp and neck area, there were multiple erythema nodules with pustules and crusts. (Figure 1) Routine blood examination, gram staining, bacterial culture, and sensitivity tests were done. The patient was then treated with Cefadroxil syrup 125 mg b.i.d with a combination of Metronidazole syrup 125 mg t.i.d., normal saline wound dressing, topical 1% salicylic acid and fusidic acid cream twice daily. The parents were also educated to maintain good hygiene of the scalp.

Figure 2. Improvement following treatment, Above: Day 8, Below: Day 16

Day 8, a-d: multiple erythematous nodules with pustules and crusts on the scalp, neck, and trunk

Day 16. a-d. Hyperpigmented macules on the scalp, neck, and trunk

On the eighth day visit, the vesicles started to heal, and no new skin lesions were found. Routine blood examination showed leukocytosis of 29.000/ μL . Gram staining showed negative-gram staining, cocci bacteria, leukocyte was 0-1/hpf. The result of the bacterial culture was *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The previous treatment was continued.

On the 16th day, no more lesions were present, leaving only hyperpigmented macules.

Discussion

This patient was diagnosed with recurrent furunculosis due to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infection based on history taking, physical examination, and supporting examination. Based on the literature, furunculosis is a deep, acute infection of the hair follicles, occurring mostly in the neck, facial, axilla, and buttocks area where sweat glands are mostly located where the skin is prone to frictional trauma. Furunculosis often do not show any constitutional symptoms, but bacteremia may occur in patients with poor nutritional status. Furunculosis in the upper lip or cheek region may cause thrombosis in the sinus cavernous. However, it is not commonly seen in patients. Recurrent furunculosis is defined as having three or more episode of infection within 12 months, as seen in our patient, and is mostly influenced by the multiple lesions and poor hygiene of our patient. It is consistent with previous studies showed that several predisposing factors that may lead to recurrent furunculosis are a family history of recurrent furunculosis, anaemia, prior antibiotic therapy, diabetes mellitus, history of the previous hospitalization, multiple lesion, poor hygiene, and other related diseases. [1-5,7,8]

Physical examination showed the consistent result as described in the literature. Furuncle usually starts as a painful, hard nodule, shown as a red folliculocentric lesion in the hairy area of the skin. Furuncle usually grows more significant, more painful, and becomes cystic in several days due to the pus accumulation inside. The pain is usually felt at the skin surrounding the furuncle, lasting for days to weeks and may be presented as a single furuncle or multiple in large areas such as the buttocks. [1,9] Several differential diagnoses should be considered when furunculosis is suspected, which are cystic acne, kerion, hidradenitis suppurativa, epidermal cyst rupture, furuncular myiasis, and osteomyelitis. [1] Diagnosis should be established based on clinical findings and supporting examination such as pus culture and gram staining.

Laboratory examination showed leukocytosis where the leukocyte count was 29.000/ μL , and the bacteria was identified as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The most common pathogen that causes furunculosis is *Staphylococcus aureus*, however other pathogens may also cause furunculosis, as seen in our patient. It is such a relief to see that most antibiotics are still able to kill the bacteria, thus confirming the effectivity of our treatment. [1,4]

Klebsiella spp. is gram-negative bacteria that belongs to the Enterobacteriaceae family. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* contributes to approximately 70% of infectious diseases in human where it colonizes the gut, skin, and nasopharyngeal area, and causes several diseases such as pneumonia, pyogenic liver abscess, and endophthalmitis. [10]. To the best of our knowledge, there are four known virulence factors of *K. pneumoniae* that enable them to evade the immune system which is hypercapsule production in HV strain, lipopolysaccharides, siderophores, and fimbria. All those factors contribute as the defence mechanism of *K. pneumoniae* in escaping the immune system. [11,12]

In several decades, erythromycin, dicloxacillin, cloxacillin, and cefalexin have been used to treat skin infections. Macrolides, cephalosporins, quinolone, and linezolid are the drug of choice in treating skin and soft tissue infections (SSTIs). Clindamycin may be used to treat recurrent furunculosis that is caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*. Penicillin or amoxicillin has not been used to treat uncomplicated SSTIs, however amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, cloxacillin, and dicloxacillin is used in treating methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) infection. Current therapy for recurrent furunculosis are both difficult

Table 1 Antibiotic sensitivity test result.

	Antibiotics	
SENSITIVE	Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid	Meropenem
	Piperazilin-tazobactam	Aztreonam
	Cephalotin	Chloramphenicol
	Cefotaxime	Trimetoprim-sulfamethoxazole
	Ceftriaxone	Cefepime
	Ceftazidime	
INTERMEDIATE	Amikacin	Imipenem
	Gentamycin	Ampicillin-sulbactam
	Tobramycin	Ticarcillin-clavulanic acid
RESISTANT	Ampicillin	

and often show the poor result. Antibiotics are recommended if there are signs of severe infection, such as multiple affected skin areas or progressing infection, immunosuppressed patients, extreme age, septic phlebitis, and not responding to incision or drainage treatment. Several antibiotics that may be used in treating furunculosis are rifampin, dicloxacillin, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline. In our patient, we gave cefadroxil syrup, 125 mg b.i.d dose combined with metronidazole syrup, 125 mg, t.i.d. Cefadroxil is a first-generation cephalosporin, a broad-spectrum antibiotic that is commonly used to treat skin infections. The known side effects of cephalosporins are much less compared to other antibiotics. Metronidazole is an antiprotozoal nitroimidazole that can be used to treat anaerobic bacterial infection. [1,2,4,13-15]

Ruptured vesicles are treated with normal saline wound dressing in the morning and evening. Normal saline solution is commonly used to treat the open wound, where the solution will provide a sterile, isotonic, and damp environment that may help in the wound healing process. Topical salicylic acid is a keratoplastic agent that may improve keratogenesis, while fusidic acid is proven effective in treating superficial skin infection and its efficacy is similar to Mupirocin. [4,16]

The main challenge in furunculosis is the spreading and recurring infection. Blood vessel invasion may occur at any time and may cause systemic infection such as osteomyelitis, acute endocarditis, or brain abscess. [1]

Conclusion

Recurrent furunculosis needs to be adequately treated to prevent potential systemic complications such as osteomyelitis, acute endocarditis, or brain abscess. Our case shows that broad-spectrum antibiotics such as cephalosporine are effective. However, sensitivity culture is still needed to determine the optimal treatment.

Disclosure Statement

There were no financial support or relationships between the authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interests.

Competing Interests

Written informed consent obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images.

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